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শান্তিনিকেতন

UNIVERSITIES IN KERALA-

- In search of Roots: A Critique on Jamaica Kincaid's - Mr. Potter- *Dr.Sangeetha Vincent- 211*
Mrs. M. Vijila Thangamalar,
Dr. R. Janatha Kumari- 221
- The Unbecoming of Women: The Need of The Hour in the Perspective of Gender- *Bijesh V Jose- 224*
Suffering as Choice: Tenets of Tradition in Buchi Emecheta's The Bride Price-
Ms. A. Naveena, Dr. R. Janatha Kumari- 234
- From Condemnation to Global Strategic Partnership : Evolution of Indo-Japan Relations-*Dr.Sivakumar M.V-238*
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EMPLOYMENT EXCHANGES IN THE
UNEMPLOYMENT SCENARIO IN KERALA : AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS- *N. K. MUNEER,*
Dr. D. Kumar, Dr. CP Shaheed Ramzan- 245
- Demystifying the Legend of Kumbalathu Sankupillai the Unsung Warrior of Kerala *Pollity-LIJI. L.-255*
Effective Recruitment Process and Organizational Performance – An Analysis- *Dr. Sanitha K K-259*
Effectiveness Of The Online Teaching-learning In Rural Assam:An Analysis- *Dr. Jayanta Baruah- 271*
An Empirical Study On Retailer Satisfaction Towards Gst With Special
Reference To Trivandrum District - *Thasni S- 276*
- VIEWING THE PAST: A POSTMODERN PERSPECTIVE ON KAZUO ISHIGURO'S *THE REMAINS*
Mrs.M.Francilin Mary, Dr.R.Selvi- 281
Dr. Manoj Kumar B- 284
OF THE DAY-
Environmental conservation- a Trans-boundary Engagement-
Survival in an Imperfect world in water Mosely's *Gone Fish in Abra- Jasly J.D, Dr. G.Yesudhas- 293*
The Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Organized And Unorganized
Retail Stores At Tirunelveli" – A Comparative Study- *P. Anis Priya, Dr. P. GEETHA- 296*
Socio-Cultural Interventions of Jamaat-e-Islami in Kerala- A Historical Perspective-
Dr. Manu T1, Dr. Hassan J2, Dr. A. K. Ampotti3- 302
- A SREEDHARA MENON :THE HISTORIAN AND HIS METHODOLOGY- *Sreerexha PL- 310*
A REVIEW ON INDUSTRIAL RELATIONS IN SOFTWARE COMPANIES WITH SPECIFIC
FOCUS ON INDUSTRIAL DISPUTE LAWS- *Viswanath V. S.- 318*
An Analytical Study of Bewildering Demand of MBA Program in Goa.- *Dr. Namdev M. Gawas- 328*
Yoga- An Alternative measure for Environmental crisis- *Praveena K K- 334*
TAX REVENUE IN INDIAN ECONOMY- *Dr. S. Sunitha- 339*
A Study On Micro Finance For The Growth Of Shgs With Special Reference To
Kanyakumari District- *Dr. S.KARTHIKEYAN- 346*
- A reading on Post Modernism and Post Colonialism in International Relations- *Dr.Riju Saimon- 355*
The Impact Of Digitalization And Msme Funding Schemes In The Economic Growth Of Women
Entrepreneur's in India- *Ms. Dhanalakshmi, Dr.A.Jesuraj, Dr. E.Joseph Rubert- 361*
R.Rajan Ganapathy-371
COGNITIVE LEARNING: AN OVERVIEW- *Dr.Sunija Beegum. N- 374*
Trends in Social Sector Expenditure in India since the 1990s-
A Thematic Analysis of Conrad's Heart of Darkness: A Study-
Capability Approach to Education : An Alternative Approach- *R.RAJAN GANAPATHY- 380*
Teaching Strategies During Covid-19 Pandemic: Challenges and Opportunities- *Shameer M.D- 386*
Sourav Naskar- 392
Rabindranath Tagore's Gateway to Japan- *Nilanjan Banerjee-400*
Historiography Of Disease, Medicine And Public Health In Colonial India: A Retrospect-
Dr. Binata Sarkar-406
- Food Security as A Critical Concern: An Analysis From the Lens of Public Distribution
System in India- *Sasmita Patel & Sasmita Padhi- 410*
Geo-Economic Appraisal of Homestay Tourism: a Case Study
Author 1: Mithun Ray,
Author 2: Tapas Sarkar- 417
Dr. Jiaul Islam-422
Indian Women and Environmental Sustainability: A Critical Analysis-
The Concept of Carbon-Credit to mitigate Global Warming- *Subrata Kumar Saha-429*

THE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ORGANIZED AND UNORGANIZED RETAIL STORES AT TIRUNELVELI" – A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Retail is currently the next sector of the Indian economy. The retail sector tends to spread rapidly in India in recent decades. The Indian retail sector consists of organized and unorganized retail markets. The retail trade includes all activities related to the sale of goods and services to consumers for personal, family or domestic use. In India, the local grocery store has long been the only choice for consumers. As increasing customer demand is driven by changing trends and aspirations for variety, traditional retailing has given rise to the modern retail format. The traditional food and grocery sector has seen the birth of supermarkets / food chains, minimarkets and hypermarkets. India is currently evolving rapidly towards an existing and competitive market with potential target consumers in the affluent and middle class categories. Quality availability, commercial space, increased product availability and brand communication are some of the factors that determine retail sales in India. The purpose of the study is to understand consumer purchasing behaviour towards organized and unorganized retail stores and to know the level of consumer satisfaction in organized retail stores and unorganized retail stores. Perception is that of traditional retailers on modern retailing. The study uses the primary data collected as part of an in-depth qualitative analysis to represent the organized and non-organized retail sectors in Tirunelveli, respectively.

Key word : Consumer Buying Behaviour, Organized Retail, Unorganized Retail, Factor Analysis

Introduction :

In India, the retail sector has grown very rapidly as most consumers are fully interested in buying goods and services from a particular location. In this scenario, Organized retail stores and Unorganized retail stores have become an essential part of the retail sector, as grocery stores continuously supply a wide range of products, according to the needs and requirements of the consumer, of everyday life. The study of consumer behaviour has become a constraint for all retailers, since the purchase of goods and services depends on consumer behaviour; they also know that positive consumer behaviour towards products and services helps the organization survive a long life.

The current retail period has shown a considerable growth in the size and market dominance of the main players in the sector, with a giant store size, greater concentration of retail trade and a wide variety of products. This has increased the level of competition in the retail trade; many small retailers

adapt their organized retail business. Increase the level of income, the high standard of living, the change in preference of urbanization, these factors attract more giants of the retail trade in India. Global retailing has grown rapidly in recent decades. Currently, the sales of the various modern sales centers are higher than those of unorganized stores, while sales of organized stores exceed by over 45% the sales of unorganized stores. In the global context, the growth of organized stores varies according to different socio-economic factors. In developed countries like the United States, organized retail sales account for about 70% of total retail sales, while in some developing countries unorganized retail sales absorbed a significant share of total sales due to changing customer preferences, increasing incomes and the lifestyle of organized trade. prevalent also in developing countries. Unorganized retail stores face competition from organized retail outlets due to financial instability or lack of presentation of unorganized retail stores.

Consumer

A person who purchases goods and services for personal use and for the manufacture or resale. The consumer is a person who can decide whether to buy an item from any product and that is influenced by marketing and advertising.

Consumer Buying Behaviour

The consumer buying behaviour refers to the purchasing behaviour of the ultimate consumer. A market must analyse purchasing behaviour to determine its reaction to the marketing strategy. Buying a particular product does not always cause the same buying behaviour. Factors such as personal, psychological and social influence consumer buying behaviour. Marketing must be aware of the three factors mentioned above to develop an adequate marketing strategy.

Retailing

Retailing is the sale of goods to end users, not for resale, but for use and consumption by the purchaser. Retailing involves the sale of goods from a single point of sale directly to a customer who intends to use that product. The retail transaction is at the end of the chain. Retail is a function of the distribution channel: an organization buys products from suppliers or makes them and sells them directly to consumers.

Organized Retailing

The organized sale refers to the commercial activities undertaken by authorized resellers, or those who are registered for sales tax, etc. these include hypermarkets and supply chains supported by the company, and even large private retail companies.

Unorganized Retailing

Unorganized retail refers to traditional low-cost formats. Retail prices, such as local kirana shops, owner-occupied department stores, pan / beedi shops, grocery stores, etc. is dominated by a large number of small retailers including local kirana shops, department stores, shoeshops, clothing stores, pan and beedi shops and street vendors etc. together form the so-called "unorganized retail trade" or traditional retail trade.

Review Of Literature

Sin and chow (2003) using the adapted version of sin and Cheung (2001) examined the quality of service of a Japanese supermarket in Hong Kong.

Terblanche & Boshoff (2006) suggested that retailers will have accept that it is not just what they market, but how it is finished. Personal interaction (face-to-face) between retail sales staff and buyers

are of crucial importance resolution areas integrated with personal interaction and new factor emerged in the study.

Kushwaha (2011) compared the perception of consumers in organized and unorganized retail market and found what factors like cleanliness, distance, price, quality, safety and space for shopping are the determining factors for unorganized retail sales.

Objectives

III To know the purchasing behaviour of consumers in relation to organized and non-organized sales outlets in Tirunelveli.

III To understand the factors that drive consumers to buy from organized and unorganized retailers

III To give suggestions to improve the services provided by organized and unorganized retailers

Methodology

In this study, an analytical method of comparative on organized and unorganized retail stores of Tirunelveli was used.

Sample

The researchers used a population-based convenience sampling method to select 208 samples from Tirunelveli.

Data collection

The study is based on primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected directly by the interviewees using the questionnaire method. Secondary data was collected in magazines and websites.

Data analysis

The primary data collected were sorted, classified and tabulated in a format and analysed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS 19.0). By deduction, an appropriate statistical procedure was used as a descriptive analysis.

Result and discussions

The main conclusions and analysis of this study are illustrated below.

Comparative analysis of Nine Factors:

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Organized and Unorganized retail store regarding Nine factors variables

Sl. No.	Particulars	Type of retail store		Total	F-Test Result
		Organized retail store	Unorganized retail store		
Interesting promotion techniques					
1	The store immediately advertises sales promotion offers	3.64	3.42	3.52	2.019
2	The shop provides informational announcements	3.38	2.81	3.08	12.283*
3	The shop always offers discounts and gifts	3.51	3.13	3.31	5.802*
4	The shop has a customer loyalty program	3.36	3.75	3.57	6.644*
5	The shop applies a different price	3.28	3.25	3.26	.040

	strategy every day	3.53	2.53	3.00	26.867*
6	The shop offers good parking				
Atmospheric shadow					
1	The shop offers a quality product	4.06	3.92	3.99	.733
2	New and fresh stocks	4.09	3.60	3.83	9.822*
3	Hygiene shop	3.79	3.62	3.70	1.110
4	Climate / comfort points	3.68	3.42	3.54	2.741
5	Clean and green shop environment	3.81	3.58	3.69	1.785
Choice of products					
1	wider product range	3.98	3.36	3.65	18.755*
2	Product displays	3.79	3.34	3.55	9.524*
3	Freedom to choose the product / brands	4.11	3.21	3.63	34.594*
4	Convenient store layout	3.77	3.32	3.53	8.731*
5	Easy to find the product and make purchases	3.57	3.36	3.46	1.721
6	Fruit and vegetable availability	3.38	3.09	3.23	2.607
7	pharmacy inside the store	2.96	2.21	2.56	17.267*
Employee service					
1	Employees are helpful and friendly	3.68	3.79	3.74	.535
2	The time taken for services is minimum	3.19	3.19	3.19	.000
3	The shop has many cash counters to reduce the time spent in the queue	3.32	2.70	2.99	11.787*
4	The shop offers good shopping fun	3.64	3.00	3.30	14.067*
5	Customer service	3.53	2.92	3.21	13.053*
6	Claim related to the title	3.40	3.32	3.36	.231
Depth of the Brand					
1	The shop has more choices and brands	4.21	3.55	3.86	16.938*
2	One-stop shop for all Grocery needs	3.77	3.49	3.62	2.640
3	Different packs are available	3.72	3.77	3.75	.091
Flexible program and return policy					
1	The store return policy is simple	3.49	3.62	3.56	.591
2	Sales people found presentable / well dressed	3.43	3.08	3.24	5.639*
3	The shop has convenient opening times	3.53	3.32	3.42	1.676
Value for the price					
1	Get the best value for money you've spent	3.79	3.64	3.71	.902
2	The price is always cheap and competitive	3.58	3.17	3.39	6.652*
Home delivery					
1	Home delivery	3.30	2.94	3.11	3.430
Comfortable payment modes					
1	The shop accepts several payment methods	3.87	2.74	3.27	33.260*

(Significant at 0.05 Level)

The above hypothesis has been accepted in several variables and rejected in several variables.

Findings

- Most respondents are women.
- Most respondents belong to the 36 to 45 age group.
- Nearly 60% of respondents are married.
- Most respondents (64%) belong to the school level.
- Some respondents are housewives (64%) and private employees (52%).
- The total monthly family income of most respondents was less than 20,000.
- 67% of respondents belonged to the nuclear family.
- The maximum number of family members was less than 3.
- The maximum number of respondents came from urban areas.
- Almost 53% of respondents prefer non-organized retail stores.
- In organized retail stores, 57.5% of respondents prefer supermarkets and in unorganized retail stores, 62.3% of respondents prefer neighbourhood / Kiran stores.
- Respondents were motivated by friends / neighbour's to purchase in organized retail stores, while in unorganized retail stores the respondents were motivated by their personal visit.
- The product purchased mainly in organized and unorganized stores was food, fruit and vegetables and food.
- Responding Respondents usually go with their spouse to buy in an organized retail store while respondents go out alone to buy at an unorganized retail store.
- The respondent's usual time in an organized retail store was less than 30-60 minutes, but in an unorganized retail store, the responder generally took less than 30 minutes.

Suggestions to unorganized retail store

- The unorganized retail store should strive to offer a wider variety of products and brands in its stores.
- The unorganized retail store must provide its customers with more informative product announcements.
- It should also provide good parking for its customers.

Suggestions to organized retail store

- The organized retail store must provide its customers with a means to replace defective products.
- Organized retailers can retain and attract customers only by adding value to their products through prices, services and offers.
- Organized retail stores should organize efficient and effective loyalty programs. This could help provide recognition to customers.

Conclusion

The study aimed to establish the impact of retail store entry on traditional stores. The impact has been studied with regard to the purchasing behaviour of consumers with respect to points of sale organized and non-organized in Tirunelveli. The results indicate that there is a clear distinction between organized and unorganized retail stores operating in the city. Although the customers of unorganized stores remain loyal to them, they also support the idea of opening new large-scale stores. This clearly shows that, for some products, the customer wants to really on an organized retail store although he is loyal to the unorganized retail store for everyday products. The study also shows that retailers are also aware of the need to bill over time. The analysis of the data also indicated that the

...seems to prefer that the point of sale maintains the price, location, services, distance and
...on the purchase.

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